

**Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe
Phase 3**

**Project management guidance
Deliverable D7.1**

EuroHPC
Joint Undertaking

This project has received funding from the EuroHPC JU under grant agreement No 101093054. Co-funded by the European Union.

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D7.1

About this document

Work package in charge: WP7 Project management

Actual delivery date for this deliverable: 28/02/2023
Dissemination level: PU (for public use)

Lead author(s): Mar Rodríguez Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC)

Other contributing author(s):
Name of institution: Name of the person writing the report

Date	Submitted by	Reviewed by	Version (notes)
20/02/2023	Mar Rodríguez (BSC)		V0.1 first draft
26/02/2023	Mar Rodríguez (BSC)	Rosa Rodríguez (BSC)	V0.2 second draft
28/02/2023	Mar Rodríguez (BSC)	Rosa Rodríguez (BSC)	V.1 final version

Contact details

Project Office: esiwace3@bsc.es

Website: www.esiwace.eu

Twitter: <https://twitter.com/esiwace>

YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/@esiwace880>

ESiWACE is on Zenodo, the Open Access repository for scientific results
<https://zenodo.org/communities/esiwace>

Disclaimer: Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European High-Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (EuroHPC JU). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Table of contents

1. Abstract /publishable summary	5
2. Conclusion & Results	5
3. Project objectives	5
4. Detailed report on the deliverable	6
4.1 Introduction	6
4.2 Project management	6
Governance structure	6
Governance bodies	7
4.3 Internal communication	9
Meetings	9
Internal mailing lists	10
Project website and internal wiki	11
4.4 Project documents	11
Types and templates	11
Documents naming rules	12
4.5 Quality assurance	12
Deliverables and milestones format	12
Deliverables review and submission	12
4.6 Monitoring and KPIs	14
Monitoring	14
Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	14
4.7 Reporting and reviews	15
National reporting	15
EuroHPC reporting and reviews	16
EuroHPC reporting	16
EuroHPC reviews	17
4.8 Risk management	17
Risks management	17
Risks management documents	19
4.9 Conflict of interest	20
5. References	20
6. Changes made and/or difficulties encountered	20
7. How this deliverable contributes to the EuroHPC strategy	20

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D7.1

8. Sustainability	20
9. Community engagement, dissemination, and exploitation	20
9.1 Target audience	20
9.2 Record of dissemination/engagement activities linked to this deliverable	21
9.3 Publications in preparation OR submitted	21
9.4 Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable	21

List of figures

Figure 1. ESiWACE3 Governance structure	6
Figure 2. Extract of the ESiWACE3 wiki	11
Figure 3. Deliverable review process	13
Figure 4. ESiWACE3 wiki: deliverables and milestones section	14
Figure 5. ESiWACE3 reporting schedule to EuroHPC	16
Figure 6. Financial reporting to EuroHPC	16
Figure 7. Technical reporting to EC process	17
Figure 8. Risk management process	18
Figure 9. Risks label classification	19

List of tables

Table 1 Governance bodies tasks	7
Table 2. Project meetings	9
Table 3. Risks management	18
Table 4. Risks rating	19

1. Abstract /publishable summary

This document provides an overview of the management and administrative procedures of the ESiWACE3 Project in order to facilitate efficient project execution as well as high-quality project results. The document will provide the ESiWACE3 consortium with a concise reference to the project management structure, tasks, and responsibilities at all levels of project execution. It establishes the management bodies and responsibilities in order to ensure timely and correct production of the results and deliverables as well as the quality and risk management plan.

2. Conclusion & Results

The main outcomes of this deliverable are the procedures and linked documents to organise and manage the project activities.

3. Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to achieving all the macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in section 1.1 of the Grant Agreement.

4. Detailed report on the deliverable

4.1 Introduction

This document specifically covers the following areas:

- Administrative project management processes that ensure accurate financial reporting and justification of the work being carried out.
- General project management processes that ensure tight coordination of project activities resulting in high-quality deliverables.
- An internal communication strategy that ensures clear and effective communication between the Partners and that allows for the early escalation and the timely resolution of possible issues concerning management and the technical work.

Changes of this document:

- The guidance is a living document. It will be regularly updated throughout the entire duration of the project to reflect the changes in - and evolution of - the project.
- The Project Manager is responsible for updating and making it available in the internal project wiki.

4.2 Project management

Governance structure

The main governing bodies of ESiWACE3 are shown on the picture below.

Figure 1. ESiWACE3 Governance structure

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D7.1

Governance bodies

The ESiWACE3 project organisation, roles and responsibilities are described in the Governance structure of the Consortium Agreement (clause 6 Governance structure). This table summarises their main tasks.

Table 1 Governance bodies tasks

Governance body	Composition	Tasks
General Assembly (GA)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All partners (beneficiaries and associated partners). • A representative of each partner. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The GA is the decision-making body of the consortium. • Each Member shall be deemed to be duly authorised to deliberate, negotiate, and decide. • Initiatives and actions on which GA takes decisions are listed in the Consortium Agreement. • Voting and veto rights are described in the Consortium Agreement.
Steering Board (SB)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project Coordinator • Project Manager • Technical Manager • Work Package leaders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Review of the project progress on a regular basis; • Making decisions on day-to-day issues. • Resource allocation, review/approval of Periodic Reports and Deliverables, preparation of project reviews, and coordination of exploitation plans. • Organisation of monthly conference calls and support of the members' involvement in decision-making. • In the case when the SB cannot obtain consensus to make a decision, bringing the issue to the General Assembly and bringing to a vote if required.
	Project Coordinator (PC)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Keeping the entire project running smoothly. • Gathering and dispensing the needed information and updating and coordinating the work throughout the project life cycle. • Ensuring internal communication in the consortium, meeting project milestones and quality control of deliverables. • Acting as the official point of contact between the Commission and the Beneficiaries.
	The Technical Manager (TM)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensuring that the scientific and technical objectives of the project are met.

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D7.1

Governance body	Composition	Tasks
Coordination team (BSC)		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Helping the PC to lead the definition of the high-level technical strategy and coordinating the team project to implement it. ● Technical presentations of project progress to external parties and ensuring the appropriate involvement and visibility of the project members. ● Close collaboration with the PC and the PM to provide clear and accurate Periodic Reports.
	Project Manager (PM)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The day-to-day execution of the project. ● Ensuring the timely achievement of project objectives and deliverables by continuously monitoring the project progress against the plan of record. ● Identify and track issues as well as propose suitable corrective actions (i.e. resource reallocation, task force creation, etc.) that might require a formal decision by the General Assembly. ● Calling the General Assembly meetings, as well as reviewing, compiling, and distributing Minutes and Actions. ● Defining the procedures for change management (proposed changes to the plan of record), risk management, quality assurance and IPR management. ● Administrative and financial management of the project. ● Monitoring internal use of resources. ● Provisioning of Periodic Reports and Financial Statements, and ensuring efficient distribution of EU funding. ● Acting as the official point of contact between the EuroHPC and the Beneficiaries.
WP leaders and Co-leaders (WPL)	WP1: BSC / JSC WP2: ECMWF / CMCC DKRZ WP3: / UH WP4: NLESC / ATOS CSC / WP5: SMHI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Coordinating the scientific and technical work of their respective Work Packages. ● Planning and control of all activities within the Work Package. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Preparing deliverables and collecting the contributions from other partners participating in the respective Work

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D7.1

Governance body	Composition	Tasks
	WP6: BSC / DKRZ WP7: BSC	<p>Packages for internal and external reports.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Participating in periodical meetings and arranging additional technical meetings when necessary. ● Supporting the Technical Manager in coordinating cross-work package relationships within the appropriate activity area. ● Actively participate in the regular project-related meetings as well as prepare technical and status presentations as required. ● Analysing the documentation of the outputs generated along the project to collect relevant information on potential marketable products. ● Supporting the partners in dealing with IPR issues as well as in negotiating joint exploitation agreements.
External Advisory Board (EAB)	External experts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ensuring the external evaluation of the project progress. ● Providing recommendations for new actions and activities in the area by liaising with the SB and participating in the general assemblies. ● Increasing the project visibility and strengthening its links to international programmes and other activities outside Europe.

4.3 Internal communication

Meetings

A part of the communication process, meetings are a key tool to monitor the project lifecycle. Regular meetings (online or face-to-face) will be held to ensure that all procedures are understood and properly implemented.

Table 2. Project meetings

Governance Body	Key responsibilities	Meetings frequency	Participants
Coordination team	Overall progress and quality of the project	Weekly	BSC
Steering Board (SB)	Follow-up of status and progress of WPs, WP tasks and synergies/alignment of work.	On monthly basis. Organised by the coordinator.	Coordination team + WP leaders.
WP Leaders	Oversee overall progress and quality of	At least, on monthly basis	WP leaders +

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D7.1

Governance Body	Key responsibilities	Meetings frequency	Participants
(WPL)	WP and WP tasks.	but it is up to WP leaders to determine the frequency with partners	task leaders and WP partners.
General Assembly (GA)	To take decisions on operational and management issues and it is responsible for all decisions of general nature within the frame of the Grant Agreement.	On annual basis. Organised by the coordinator and the partner host.	All partners.
External Advisory Board (EAB)	To make recommendations on project objective achievements and impact.	At least four times during the project duration. Back-to-back with General Assemblies.	EAB members and coordination team (if needed)

The initiator of the meeting (coordinator, WP leaders, etc) is responsible for:

- sending the meeting request,
- organising the meeting locations and facilities (if needed),
- ensuring that meeting minutes are sent to the Coordinator and archived in the project wiki.

Internal mailing lists

Having proper communication within the project is one of the main goals of good project management. The ESiWACE3 project has developed several internal tools to improve the information flows within the project.

The website and the internal wiki will be the main tools for the project communication with the outer world and internally, respectively. The partners are strongly encouraged to visit them and send feedback to the project office. A set of mailing lists, which have been pre-populated by the Coordinator, are available for all the partners. Some examples of the addresses created are:

- General lists:
 - research_ew3@bsc.es: this list is addressed to all researchers in the project.
 - management_ew3@bsc.es: this list addresses those contacts in charge of legal, financial, and administrative issues in each partner institution.
- WP lists:
 - wpleaders_ew3@bsc.es: this list is addressed only to the WP leaders and co-leaders.
 - wp1_ew3@bsc.es
 - wp2_ew3@bsc.es
 - wp3_ew3@bsc.es
 - wp4_ew3@bsc.es
 - wp5_ew3@bsc.es
 - wp6_ew3@bsc.es
 - wp7_ew3@bsc.es

The control of WP lists will be handed back to the WP leaders. The instructions on how to manage the mailing lists can be found in the wiki. The coordinator will moderate general lists and WP list will be unmoderated. Partners' remote internal communications can be held through online platforms. The preparation of minutes is strongly recommended, and any minutes should be uploaded to the wiki.

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D7.1

Project website and internal wiki ESiWACE3

website

The project website will be available in a public link: <https://www.esiwace.eu/>
This website is a legacy of the previous two phases ESiWACE and ESiWACE2.

WP6 is responsible for the management and update of the project website. Details will be provided in the deliverable *D6.1 Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan*.

ESiWACE3 internal wiki

The ESiWACE3 internal wiki is a private section of the web area and can be accessed via the external website or directly through the link It is only available after registration, which is controlled by the coordination team.

This wiki is an important communication tool of the consortium. It has been designed to exchange documents and as a repository of discussions and information in general. The access to the wiki is subject to coordinator's approval. All partners have been invited to register and encouraged to use this tool.

Figure 2. Extract of the ESiWACE3 wiki

The information is constantly supervised by the coordination team and updated by partners and the coordinator.

4.4 Project documents

Types and templates

The ESiWACE3 project has different templates depending on the type of reporting and WP, as listed below:

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D7.1

- Deliverable template
- Milestone template
- Minutes Template
- Blank ESiWACE3 pptx template
- Risk and Issue process templates

Templates are provided and stored in the project internal wiki under the "Logos and templates" section". All templates are aligned with the visual identity of ESiWACE3, and those used for public communication have the EU acknowledgement emblem. If any other template is needed, the WP6 will design it upon request.

WP6 leader institution is responsible for maintaining and storing project templates.

Documents naming rules

To ensure the track of document versions and avoid missing information, ESiWACE3 has foreseen general naming rules for the documents released in the project:

- Deliverables and milestones must respect the general naming rule:

DX.X_vN
MY.Y_vN

- DX.X represents the deliverable number.
- vN.n represents a simplified version number for the internally reviewed versions (as we can rely on the project wiki)
- v0.x (for v0.1 to v0.9 for initial drafts versions)
- v1.1 (v1.2, etc.) ... for complete version, under review and candidates for official delivery.
- v1 for the reviewed official version submitted to the Commission.
- v2, v3, etc. for further updates.

4.5 Quality assurance

Deliverables and milestones format

Templates for the deliverables and milestones has been created in WP6 and are available in the project wiki as mentioned in section 3.

Deliverables review and submission

The list of deliverables and milestones y available in the project wiki and regularly updated by the Deliverable Leader. The Internal review process goes through stages (depicted in Figure 2) to ensure that any issues concerning the overall quality is resolved before final approval and submission of deliverables to the EuroHPC or publication of the report. The Coordinator is responsible for the Quality assurance process that starts 1 months before the official deadline.

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D7.1

Figure 3. Deliverable review process

1 Draft preparation

- The Coordinator will send an alert message to the Deliverable leader and to the corresponding WP Leader.
- It is up to the Deliverable leader to organise the way to collect the information and organise partners' contribution to the document.
- A full draft of the deliverable/milestone should be made available to the Coordinator and WP leader in the next 20 days. Partners involved will contribute to the deliverable/milestone along this period.

2 Deliverable review

- The WP leader, supported by the Deliver leader, will appoint a reviewer. This reviewer should be an expert in the topic (internal or external) not directly involved in the preparation of the deliverable/milestone.
- The WP leader, Deliverable leader, partners involved and reviewer expert, will have 15 days to grant approval or suggest modifications to this draft. The approval of the final version is granted by the reviewer.
- In case a deeper re-work appears necessary, the reviewer(s) are asked to provide constructive suggestions for improvement in writing to the Deliverable Leader and WP leader. Upon receiving the suggestions for improvement, the Coordination Team works with the Deliverable Lead beneficiary to determine the schedule to complete the Deliverable.
- The Deliverable leader is responsible for the final check and implementation of the potential changes. They will have ten days for this process. The final version should be made available in the project wiki.

3 Deliverable submission

- The Coordinator will be responsible for collecting the final deliverable and submitting it to the Research Participant Portal tool.
- Final version will be available in the project wiki under the section "Deliverables and Milestones" (Figure 4). Stable versions should always be provided as an additional PDF file. Deliverables and milestones documents must follow the naming rules mentioned above.

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D7.1

Figure 4. ESIWACE3 wiki: deliverables and milestones section

4.6 Monitoring and KPIs

Monitoring

The Coordination team observes and checks the progress of the project keeping a systematic internal review.

Technical monitoring:

- The scientific work will be supervised by the Coordinator and supported by the WP leaders. Each WP leader shall organise the work and the communication within their work package. If needed, the Coordinator may ask for a summary status report at any stage of the project.
- The WP leaders and the Coordinator will meet remotely on a monthly, during the first GA a different periodicity might be decided; extra meetings are foreseen upon request. These meetings will report the progress of the work done and deviations of the project plan, if any. The minutes will be made available in the project wiki.

Deliverables/Milestones monitoring

The preparation of deliverables is responsibility of Deliverable leaders under the supervision of WP leader. A set of templates has been, and they will be available, in the project wiki. The monitoring process is explained in section 4 of this deliverable.

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D7.1

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

Definition

The ESiWACE3 project has defined a set of KPIs to monitor the proper development of the project.

- KPIs are aligned with project objectives and have a specific target to be achieved by the end of the project.
- The list of KPIs will be available in the project wiki under the section "WP7 Project management".

Measurement and refining

- KPIs measuring is planned on a six-monthly basis, and results are presented during the corresponding annual General Assemblies.
- In case the WPs activity developed makes it inappropriate to continue reporting on the same KPIs or happened that they are not relevant over time, this KPI list will be refined to facilitate the reporting.
- The Steering Board is responsible for ensuring the KPIs follow-up.

4.7 Reporting and reviews

Since ESiWACE3 project is co-funded by EuroHPC/EC and the national agencies of beneficiaries' national agencies, reporting is subject to two reporting levels:

- National reporting: Partners reporting to the coordinator.
- External reporting: Periodic reporting to EC and national agencies.

The next sections explain how to proceed in both cases.

National reporting

The EuroHPC JU member states participating in ESiWACE3 project are: France, Germany, Italy, the Netherlands, Spain and Sweden. The national agencies from these countries will co-fund ESiWACE3 up to 50% according to their rules.

All beneficiaries, except ECMWF, should contact their national agencies to ensure the corresponding requirements and criteria are fulfilled. The ECMWF, as an international organisation, will co-fund its budget with their own resources.

On annual basis, the coordinator will request to beneficiaries an update of the national co-funding status and the impact on the project activities, if any.

EuroHPC reporting and reviews

EuroHPC reporting

Figure 5. ESiWACE3 reporting schedule to EuroHPC

The ESiWACE3 project reports to the EuroHPC according to its rules and through the Research Participant Portal. This external reporting consists of two parts: a financial report and a technical report. Once the Periodic Reporting session is open on the Research Participant Portal website, the Coordinator will send an alert email to the consortium for collecting the information and providing the corresponding instructions.

Individual Financial report:

Each partner is responsible for its financial report to the EuroHPC JU. The financial statements submission is made individually by each partner through the grant management system, which is available in the Research Participant Portal.

The rules and explanations for fulfilling the financial reports can be found on the [Horizon Europe Online Manual](#) under the section Periodic reports and also in the project wiki.

The process is summarised in the following picture:

Figure 6. Financial reporting to EuroHPC

Technical report:

This report consists of two parts, Part A and Part B, and the Coordinator is responsible for submitting both

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D7.1

parts through the Research Participant Portal. All partners are responsible for providing the information to the Coordinator in order to complete the technical report which describes the project progress during the period reported.

The internal reporting (see above section 5.2.1) is the basis of this technical report. The process is summarised in the following picture:

Figure 7. Technical reporting to EC process

EuroHPC reviews

In parallel with the reporting to the EuroHPC and according to the grant agreement no 101093054 article 25, the ESiWACE3 project is subject to three reviews.

They will be formally notified by the EuroHPC to the coordinator and will be considered to start on the date of the notification. The coordination team will work with WP leaders and the rest of partners to reply to the review requests.

It is expected that reviews will be organised as in person meetings as shows in the table below.

Review no	Tentative date	Venue
1	December 2023	Luxembourg
2	June 2025	Luxembourg
3	December 2026	Luxembourg

4.8 Risk management

Risks management

The ESiWACE3 project has established the following process to ensure the proper monitoring of projects risks:

Figure 8. Risk management process

The above process will be applied to each WP for monitoring project risks. The following table shows the management bodies involved in the process responsibilities and frequency of risks follow up. The coordination team is responsible for ensuring the whole process.

Table 3. Risks management

Who	What	When	Documents to be used
Coordination team	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● It is responsible for coordinating risks management. ● To collect WPs risks and integrate them into the risks matrix. ● To ensure the follow-up of risks status. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● On a monthly basis. ● Risk information is collected one week before each Management Board meeting. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Table of risks (available in the wiki) ● Risks matrix integrated ● Integrated mitigation plan (if needed)
WP Leaders (WPL)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● To identify the foreseen and unforeseen risks of their WP. ● To report to the Management Board using the WP risks register template (available in the wiki) ● To propose mitigation measures, if needed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● On a monthly basis but it is up to WP leaders to determine the frequency. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Table of risks ● WP risks register ● WP risks mitigation plan (if needed)
Steering Board (SB)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● To analyse and assess project risks based on the information provided by WP leaders. ● To agree on the mitigation measures. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● On a monthly basis. ● If needed, extra meetings devoted to risks management are also foreseen. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Table of risks ● Integrated Risks matrix ● Integrated mitigation plan

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D7.1

Risks management documents

There are several documents that will help to collect the risks information:

- Grant Agreement Part A: It includes the table of risks foreseen in the project.
- WP risks register: this document is a table with several columns that include, among other information, the likelihood and Impact score of the risk and mitigation action plan when needed. Unforeseen risks will be also included in this table.
- Risk matrix: this table summarizes the list of risks and gives an overview of the risks status.
- Templates of these documents are available in the project wiki.

Figure 9. Risks label classification

Risks matrix will reflect the level of risks according to the labels that are classified in Low, Medium and High. Decisions on the action plan will be taken accordingly as shown in the table below:

Table 4. Risks rating

Rating	Decision	Description
HIGH	Avoid	Find a way to avoid the risk. For example, by taking a different approach, not doing something, using different tools, etc.
MEDIUM	Mitigate	Find a way to reduce the likelihood of the risk occurring or the severity of the impact if the risk does occur.
LOW	Accept	The risk is acceptable. The project can move forward, and mitigation of the risk is a low priority.

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D7.1

4.9 Conflict of interest

The goodwill to avoid any conflict of interest and to act in good faith is essential for a project like ESIWACE3. When Partners identify conflicts of interest which cannot be resolved through bilateral communication, they should bring the issues to the attention of the Coordination team immediately. The Coordination team will in turn bring the issue to the Steering Board and, if is needed, to the General Assembly for discussion and a vote if required.

Each partner must take all measures to prevent any situation where the impartial and objective implementation of the specific tasks assigned to each partner is compromised for reasons involving economic interest, political or national affinity, family or emotional ties or any other conflicting interest ('conflict of interests').

The Consortium Agreement signed within the consortium will also help to regulate the relationship among partners.

5. References

N/A

6. Changes made and/or difficulties encountered

N/A

7. How this deliverable contributes to the EuroHPC strategy

N/A

8. Sustainability

The present deliverable sets the basic rules for managing and monitoring the work. WPs will follow the guidance of this deliverable to ensure the alignment work with the project objectives.

9. Community engagement, dissemination, and exploitation

9.1 Target audience

As indicated in the Grant Agreement, the audience for this deliverable is:

	The general public (PU).
X	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This report is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D7.1

This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience, it will be available in the following platforms:

- The internal project wiki
- The project website, since this is a public deliverable.
- The [Research Participant Portal](#) under the ESiWACE3 project section.

9.2 Record of dissemination/engagement activities linked to this deliverable

N/A

9.3 Publications in preparation OR submitted

N/A

9.4 Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable

N/A